

MOTIVATEXR

Maintenance, Support & Operation Training using Immersive Virtual and Augmented Technology for Efficiency with XR

D6.1 - CONTINUOUS INTEGRATION PLAN AND PLATFORM

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D6.1 – CONTINUOUS INTEGRATION PLAN AND PLATFORM

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document outlines the Continuous Integration (CI) strategies implemented to ensure the integration of the platform and the integration of the outcomes from WP4 and WP5 of MOTIVATE XR project. By fostering collaboration and streamlining deployment processes, this plan ensures that MOTIVATE XR releases are robust, secure, and adaptable to the diverse needs of the ecosystem.

This deliverable consists of the following sections

- **Section 1 – Introduction:** Provides the purpose of the document, an overview of the MOTIVATE XR architecture, and highlights the benefits of continuous integration.
- **Section 2 – GitLab Repository Structure:** Describes a workshop conducted with the tool owners to understand their technical needs and their approach to integrating the tool within the platform
- **Section 3 – Environments:** Describes the key platform interactions and scenarios, including user access via the dashboard, third-party tool integration, API authentication, and internal service usage.
- **Section 4 – CI/CD Overview:** Outlines the stages of the CI/CD pipeline, including build, test, deploy, and publish, to ensure smooth integration and deployment.
- **Section 5 – GitLab CI Configuration:** Details the setup of GitLab CI, including runner configuration, gitlab-ci.yml, environment variables, and monitoring practices.
- **Section 6 – Automated Testing:** Emphasizes the importance of automated tests to maintain quality and reliability throughout the development process.
- **Section 7 – Tools Integration** Presents the methods and outcomes of integrating MOTIVATE XR tools, including API-based and dashboard-based options tailored to each tool's requirements.
- **Section 8 – Conclusions:** Provides an overview of the contents with projections about the next steps.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Title
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
BIM	Building Information Modelling
CAD	Computer-Aided Design
CD	Continuous Deployment
CI	Continuous Integration
CMS	Content Management System
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRUD	Create Read Update Delete
CSRF	cross-site request forgery
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
IdP	Identity Provider
MR	Mixed Reality
NAS	Network Attached Storage
NeRFs	Neural Radiance Fields
OAuth	Open Authentication
SDK	Software Development Kit
UAT	User Acceptance Testing
VSLAM	Visual Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
VR	Virtual Reality
XR	Extended Reality
XSS	Cross-site Scripting

1 INTRODUCTION

Extended Reality (XR) is poised to revolutionize the way industries approach training, assistance, and operational workflows. By encompassing augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR), and mixed reality (MR), XR offers immersive experiences that can significantly enhance the effectiveness of industrial processes. This is particularly impactful in complex tasks such as assembly, manufacturing, maintenance, and dismantling of industrial goods, where traditional methods of training and assistance may fall short.

MOTIVATE XR aims to be a collaborative tool suite for authoring, publishing, and experiencing XR content. The platform is designed to facilitate seamless collaboration among multiple stakeholders involved in industrial operations, providing tools for effective training and assistance. The ability to create, distribute, and manage XR content collaboratively ensures that industries can streamline their processes, improve safety, reduce errors, and enhance the overall efficiency of their operations.

To achieve this, a powerful Content Management System (CMS) is crucial for managing the XR content lifecycle. The CMS allows the platform to effectively organize, store, and distribute XR assets, ensuring that the right content is available at the right time for users and third-party tools. By leveraging a robust CMS, MOTIVATE XR provides a foundation that supports scalability, flexibility, and ease of use, enabling industries to harness the full potential of XR technologies in their workflows.

1.1 PURPOSE OF THE DOCUMENT

The purpose of this document is to outline a Continuous Integration (CI) and Continuous Deployment (CD) plan for the cybersecure MOTIVATE XR platform, that is used to manage and deploy applications. As this is the first version of the document, it will explain the workflow and of the CI/CD in a staging environment hosted by UPM and transitioning to a self-hosted Kubernetes environment. The final CI plan with the production environment will be provided on D6.2.

1.2 OVERVIEW OF THE MOTIVATE XR ARCHITECTURE

The MOTIVATE XR Cybersecure Architecture is a comprehensive platform designed to securely manage, store, and distribute XR files. It serves as a centralized hub that not only facilitates user interaction with XR content but also provides seamless access for third-party applications and tools.

The platform architecture is built around a containerized and customized open-source headless CMS. By using containerization, the platform ensures scalability and easy deployment across various environments. Integrated with a secure SQL database, it efficiently stores and retrieves XR files and metadata. A public Application Programming Interface (API) with layered cybersecurity—including Open Authorization (OAuth) and API keys—will allow authorized external tools to interact safely with the CMS. For users, a dashboard will provide a simple interface to manage XR content with real-time updates. Additionally, an Identity Provider (IdP) will handle authentication and authorization, ensuring only verified users and tools can access the platform. This setup aims to offer secure, scalable, and customizable content management that integrates smoothly with third-party tools. More detailed specifications of the Cybersecure Architecture are provided in the D3.5 “Functional Specifications & Cybersecure Architecture” document.

1.3 BENEFITS OF THE CI

Implementing a Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) pipeline provides significant advantages for MOTIVATEXR’s development lifecycle, ensuring efficiency, quality, and collaboration. One of the primary benefits of CI/CD is automated testing, which guarantees that only code passing predefined quality checks is integrated into the main development branches, leading to potential reduction in the risk of introducing defects. This consistent validation process maintains the stability of the codebase and ensures that each update meets project standards.

Another key advantage of CI/CD is efficient Docker image management, where the process of building and pushing images is fully automated. This feature not only minimizes manual effort but also reduces the risk of errors, ensuring that every new version is reliably prepared for deployment. Additionally, the pipeline enables controlled releases, supporting structured release schedules and aligning deployments with project milestones and operational requirements.

The use of a CI/CD pipeline also enhances collaboration among developers by enforcing consistent branching and merging strategies. This structured approach fosters better coordination within the team, ensuring a smoother integration of contributions. Finally, the rigorous testing and deployment practices integral to CI/CD significantly improve code quality, minimizing the risk of bugs or regressions in production. These combined benefits make a CI/CD pipeline an essential tool for ensuring robust, efficient, and high-quality project delivery.

2 GITLAB REPOSITORY STRUCTURE

The UPM primarily utilizes GitLab as the platform for hosting and managing its code repositories. In line with this practice, the MOTIVATEX R's Cybersecure Development project will also leverage GitLab's robust infrastructure, allowing all related repositories to be securely hosted in private repositories.

2.1 BRANCHING STRATEGY

MOTIVATE XR employs a structured branching strategy within GitLab to streamline collaboration and uphold high standards of code quality. This strategy revolves around two main branches, main and dev, along with feature-specific and bug-fix branches that promote a clean and organized workflow.

2.1.1 MAIN BRANCH

The main branch serves as the production-ready codebase and represents the stable version of the application currently deployed. This branch is protected to ensure it remains free from untested or unstable changes. Updates to the main branch occur only when a new release has been thoroughly validated and approved, ensuring that production always reflects reliable and high-quality code.

2.1.2 DEV BRANCH

The dev branch acts as the primary integration branch where active development takes place. Developers create individual branches for new features or bug fixes, branching off from the dev branch. The dev branch is periodically prepared for a new release. At this stage, the dev branch undergoes comprehensive testing, which includes automated tests, peer code reviews, and deployment to a staging environment, if necessary. These tests simulate production-like conditions to identify and resolve potential issues before release. Once the dev branch satisfies all quality standards, it is merged into the main branch, marking the code as production-ready and eligible for deployment.

This structured approach ensures a clear separation between the development and production environments, providing multiple benefits that enhance both efficiency and reliability. By fully validating changes before deployment, this approach significantly reduces the risk of introducing instability into the production environment. Additionally, it simplifies the tracking and management

of changes, making it easier to implement rollbacks when necessary. Furthermore, isolating individual contributions until they are ready for integration fosters a more collaborative development process, enabling developers to work independently while maintaining the integrity of the shared codebase.

2.1.3 FEATURE/HOTFIX BRANCHES

For every new feature or bug fix, a dedicated branch is created from the dev branch to isolate new features or bug fixes. These branches are named descriptively to indicate their purpose, such as *feature/user-authentication* or *bugfix/login-error*. By isolating work into dedicated branches, developers can focus on their tasks without risking interference with the main development workflow. Once a feature or fix is completed, tested locally, and reviewed, it is merged back into the dev branch. This process ensures that incomplete or unstable changes do not impact the overall progress of development.

2.2 MERGE POLICIES AND RULES

To maintain code quality and ensure stability, the project enforces strict merge policies and rules.

2.2.1 CODE REVIEW REQUIREMENTS

Before any branch is merged into the dev or main branches, the code must undergo a thorough peer review. This process requires at least one other developer to reviews the changes, to ensure they comply with the project's coding standards, are well-documented, and do not introduce any new issues. Code reviews promote knowledge sharing, improve code quality, and help identify potential problems early in the development process.

2.2.2 AUTOMATES TESTING PREREQUISITES

Automated testing is a critical component of the merge process. Before merging, all changes must pass a suite of automated tests, which may include unit tests, integration tests, and other quality checks. If any test fails, the merge is blocked until the issues are resolved. This process ensures that only code that meets predefined quality standards is integrated into the dev or main branches.

2.2.3 MERGING RULES

	Merging into dev	Merging into main
Prerequisites	Code review approval from at least one other developer.	Comprehensive testing on the dev branch, including automated tests and possibly staging deployments to validate the new code under conditions that mimic production.
	All automated tests pass successfully.	All code review comments are addressed.
Process	Developer submits a merge request from the feature/hotfix branch to the dev branch.	A merge request is created from the dev branch to the main branch.
	The CI/CD pipeline runs automated tests.	Final verification is performed, ensuring all quality standards are met.
	After passing tests and receiving code review approval, the merge is completed.	Upon approval, the merge is completed.
	The version number is incremented appropriately (minor or patch).	The major version number is incremented.

TABLE 1 MERGING RULES

2.3 VERSIONING

MOTIVATE XR platform adopts a standardized versioning strategy based on Semantic Versioning (SemVer) to maintain clarity, consistency, and predictability throughout the development lifecycle. This approach ensures that all stakeholders have a clear understanding of the scope and impact of changes made to the software.

2.3.1 SEMANTIC VERSIONING (SEMVER)

Semantic Versioning follows the format **MAJOR.MINOR.PATCH**, where each segment of the version number signifies the nature of the changes:

- **MAJOR version (X.0.0):** Incremented for incompatible API changes or significant modifications that may not be backward-compatible.
- **MINOR version (0.Y.0):** Incremented when new features or enhancements are added in a backward-compatible manner.
- **PATCH version (0.0.Z):** Incremented for backward-compatible bug fixes or **Version Increment Rules**.

Patch Version Increment (X.Y.Z → X.Y.(Z+1))

- **When to Increment:**
 - Fixing bugs or defects that do not affect the API or functionalities.
 - Making minor improvements or optimizations.
- **Examples:**
 - Correcting a minor bug that doesn't alter application behavior significantly.
 - Making small performance enhancements.

Minor Version Increment (X.Y.Z → X.(Y+1).0)

- **When to Increment:**
 - Adding new features or enhancements that are backward-compatible.
 - Introducing new functionalities without breaking existing APIs.
- **Examples:**
 - Implementing a new feature module.
 - Adding new endpoints to an existing API.

Major Version Increment (X.Y.Z → (X+1).0.0)

- **When to Increment:**
 - Making changes that are not backward compatible.
 - Removing or significantly altering existing functionalities.
 - Overhauling system architecture or core components.
- **Examples:**
 - Refactoring the application in a way that changes existing API behaviors.
 - Eliminating deprecated features that clients might still use.

2.3.2 VERSIONING ACROSS BRANCHES

To maintain consistency and clarity throughout the development process, a versioning strategy is applied across different branches in a structured manner. This makes sure that each branch accurately reflects the state of the code and its readiness for deployment.

- **Feature/Hotfix Branches:**
 - Utilize pre-release identifiers (e.g., **1.3.0-beta.1**) during development.
 - Helps in tracking progress and testing pre-release versions.
- **Dev Branch:**
 - **MINOR** and **PATCH** versions are incremented upon successful merges of features or bug fixes.
 - Reflects the cumulative changes ready for staging and further testing.
- **Main Branch:**
 - **MAJOR** version is incremented when merging into the main branch for a production release.
 - Signifies a release with significant updates or potential breaking changes.

2.3.3 TAGGING AND RELEASE PROCESS

An organized tagging and release process is essential for tracking changes, facilitating rollbacks, and communicating updates to stakeholders. This strategy incorporates systematic tagging and detailed release notes to effectively document each version.

- **Docker Tagging:**
 - Each release is tagged in the Docker repository using the version number.
- **Git Tagging:**
 - Each release is tagged in the Git repository using the version number.
- **Release Notes:**
 - Document the details of each release, categorized by:
 - New Features
 - Bug Fixes
 - Breaking Changes
 - Deprecations
 - Provide migration guides, if necessary, especially for major releases.

2.3.4 INTEGRATION WITH CI/CD PIPELINE

Integrating versioning strategy with the CI/CD pipeline automates version management and enforces consistency across the development process. This integration enables version increments and changelogs to be handled systematically, reducing manual effort and potential errors.

- **Automated Version Bumping:**
 - The CI/CD pipeline automates version number increments based on commit messages or merge actions.
 - Uses tools or scripts to update version numbers consistently.
- **Changelog Generation:**
 - Automatically generates or updates the changelog with details from commit messages or pull requests.
 - Ensures transparency and keeps all stakeholders informed.
- **Compliance Checks:**
 - The pipeline includes checks to ensure version numbers follow SemVer rules.
 - Prevents accidental releases without proper version increments.

3 ENVIRONMENTS

MOTIVATE XR project employs a multi-tiered development environment strategy to maintain code quality, facilitate thorough testing, and streamline the deployment process. This approach involves three primary environments—Local, Staging, and Production—each serving a specific purpose in the development lifecycle and allowing for a controlled and efficient progression of code from inception to deployment.

3.1 LOCAL ENVIRONMENT

The Local Environment is where individual developers write, compile, and test their code on their personal machines. In this setting, developers have the freedom to experiment with new features, fix bugs, and perform initial testing without impacting the shared codebase. They can customize their development setup with tools and configurations that enhance productivity and run unit tests to validate the functionality of individual components before integration. Working in isolated local environments enables developers to iterate rapidly, catch errors early, and verify their code meets initial quality standards before sharing it with the team.

3.2 STAGING ENVIRONMENT

Serving as a critical intermediary between development and production, the Staging Environment closely replicates the production environment. It provides a platform to simulate production conditions by mirroring hardware, software, and network configurations, which helps in identifying environment-specific issues. In the staging environment, code from the dev branch, including the latest merged features and fixes, is deployed. This environment allows for comprehensive testing, including integration testing to ensure different modules and services work together seamlessly, system testing to validate the complete and integrated software product, and User Acceptance Testing (UAT), where stakeholders verify that the system meets business requirements. The staging environment is essential for identifying and resolving issues such as bugs, performance bottlenecks, or security vulnerabilities that may not be apparent in the local environment. By serving as the final testing ground, it ensures that code is production-ready and reduces the risk of issues upon deployment.

UPM will provide this environment, a Kubernetes cluster with three nodes, which will try to closely mirror the production setup to provide an accurate testing ground for the platform. Each node is provisioned with ample Central Processing Unit (CPU) and memory resources to effectively handle the anticipated load during testing phases. The Kubernetes cluster includes essential components such as an Ingress controller to manage external access. It uses ConfigMaps and Secrets for dynamic configuration and sensitive data management. A Network Attached Storage (NAS) has been integrated for persistent storage solutions using Persistent Volume Claims (PVCs) to support stateful applications and data persistence across deployments. Monitoring and logging tools like Prometheus and Grafana could be installed, enabling real-time performance tracking and facilitating prompt identification and resolution of issues. HTTPS with SSL/TLS protocols will be implemented throughout the environment. This setup enables encrypted connections between clients and services, safeguarding data in transit. SSL/TLS certificates are securely managed and integrated with the Ingress controller to terminate HTTPS connections, providing secure external access to the services running within the cluster.

3.3 PRODUCTION ENVIRONMENT

The Production Environment is the live system where the application is available to end-users. Hosting the code from the main branch, this environment is characterized by stability and reliability, as only thoroughly tested and approved code is deployed to guarantee a dependable user experience. Strict access controls are in place to prevent unauthorized changes, maintaining the integrity of the live application. Continuous monitoring and maintenance are critical in this environment, with performance monitoring to detect and address issues proactively and robust security measures to protect user data and system integrity. The deployment process is carefully controlled, with manual release triggers allowing for oversight and coordination, and rollback

capabilities available in case critical issues are discovered. The production environment represents the culmination of the development process, delivering value to users and reflecting the project's success.

Details of the production environment will be included in the Deliverable D6.2.

4 CI/CD OVERVIEW

After code changes are merged into the dev or main branch, the Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) pipeline is automatically triggered to streamline the integration of new features and maintain high code quality. This workflow is composed of four critical stages: Build, Test, Deploy, and Publish. The first three stages are triggered by merging into the Dev branch, while the publish stage is only triggered when merging into the main branch. Each stage plays a vital role in ensuring that the application is thoroughly tested, securely packaged, and efficiently deployed to both the staging and production environments.

4.1 BUILD STAGE

The Build stage initiates the CI/CD pipeline by constructing Docker images based on the latest code from the dev branch. This process involves compiling the application code and encapsulating it within Docker containers, along with all necessary dependencies and environment configurations. By containerizing the application, the consistency is achieved across different deployment environments, reducing environment problems. The Docker images serve as the standardized units for subsequent testing and deployment phases, ensuring that the same artifact is tested and eventually deployed to production.

4.2 TEST STAGE

Following the successful build of Docker images, the pipeline progresses to the **Test** stage. Here, a comprehensive suite of automated tests is executed to validate the integrity and functionality of the application components.

The Test stage is crucial for detecting bugs, regressions, or any unintended side effects introduced by recent code changes. If any tests fail, the pipeline halts, and developers are notified to address the issues before proceeding. This gatekeeping mechanism maintains the overall quality and stability of the codebase.

4.3 DEPLOY STAGE

After successfully passing all tests, the pipeline proceeds to the Deploy stage. In this stage, the newly built and tested Docker images are retrieved from a registry, such as Docker Hub or GitLab's Container Registry, and deployed to the Kubernetes Staging Environment by pulling the latest Docker images.

Deploying to staging enables the team to validate deployment scripts and configurations, making sure that Kubernetes functions correctly. It also provides an opportunity to perform manual and exploratory testing, identifying any issues that automated tests might have missed. Additionally, the team can conduct performance and load testing to allow external tools to verify their integration with the platform. This stage is essential for catching any environment-specific issues and providing a final verification before the application is promoted to production.

4.4 PUBLISH STAGE

The final stage involves updating the Production Environment with the latest application version. The CI/CD pipeline triggers a rolling update on the production Kubernetes cluster, deploying the newly built Docker images. Kubernetes orchestrates the update by replacing the old pods with new ones running the updated application, ensuring minimal downtime and a seamless transition.

Lorem ipsum

5 GITLAB CONFIGURATION

The Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) pipeline is orchestrated using GitLab CI/CD, configured through the `.gitlab-ci.yml` file located at the root of the repository. This configuration defines the stages, jobs, and scripts that automate the building, testing, deployment, and publishing of the application. The pipeline ensures that code changes are systematically processed and deployed, maintaining consistency and reliability across environments.

5.1 GITLAB RUNNER CONFIGURATION

To execute the CI/CD pipeline, a self-hosted GitLab Runner is utilized within the environment. This runner is installed on dedicated servers and is responsible for running the pipeline jobs defined in the `.gitlab-ci.yml` file. By hosting the runner internally, greater control over the execution environment is gained, including:

- **Security:** All code and artifacts remain within the infrastructure, reducing exposure to external threats.

- **Customization:** The runner environment can be tailored with specific tools, dependencies, and configurations required for the projects.
- **Resource Management:** Resources such as CPU, memory, and storage can be allocated according to needs, ensuring optimal performance.

The runner is registered with the internal GitLab instance using a unique token and is tagged appropriately (e.g., `motivatexr-runner`). This tag is used in the CI configuration to direct jobs to the self-hosted runner. The runner is configured to run with the Docker executor, allowing each job to run in an isolated Docker container, which enhances security and consistency.

5.2 GITLAB-CI.YML

The `gitlab-ci.yml` file is structured into the four primary stages defined on section 4 CI/CD Overview. Each stage contains specific jobs that execute sequentially, ensuring that the application is thoroughly built, tested, and deployed.

5.2.1 BUILD STAGE

In the Build stage, the job `build` compiles the application and builds Docker images. The script executes commands to build the application and package it within Docker containers. After building, any running Docker Compose services are shut down to clean up the environment.

5.2.2 TEST STAGE

The Test stage contains the job `test`, which runs automated tests to validate the application's functionality. The application is started in a development environment using Docker Compose, and tests are executed inside the Docker container. Upon completion, Docker Compose services are shut down.

5.2.3 DEPLOY STAGE

In the Deploy stage, the job `deploy` handles the deployment to the Kubernetes Staging Environment. The script starts the application, logs into the Docker registry securely using environment variables (e.g., `DOCKER_PASSWORD`), and pushes the Docker images to the registry. After pushing the images, Docker Compose services are shut down on the runner, and finally the Kubernetes staging cluster is triggered to update its pods with the latest images.

5.2.4 PUBLISH STAGE

The Publish stage includes the job `publish`, responsible for deploying the application to the Production Environment. This stage triggers the Kubernetes production cluster to update its pods, ensuring that the latest version of the application is running in production.

5.3 EXAMPLE GITLAB-CI.YAML FILE

Below is an example of the `.gitlab-ci.yml` file, with scripts represented in pseudocode to focus on the structure and flow of the pipeline:

```
stages:
  - build
  - test
  - deploy
  - publish
build:
  stage: build
  script:
    - # Build the application and create Docker images
    - # Shut down any running Docker Compose services
  only:
    - dev
  tags:
    - motivatexr-runner

test:
  stage: test
  script:
    - # Start the application in a development environment using Docker Compose
    - # Execute automated tests inside the Docker container
    - # Shut down Docker Compose services after testing
  only:
    - dev
  tags:
    - motivatexr-runner

deploys:
  stage: deploy
```

```
script:
  - # Start the application
  - # Log in to the Docker registry securely
  - # Push the Docker images to the registry
  - # Shut down Docker Compose services
  - # Trigger the Kubernetes Staging Environment to update pods
only:
  - dev
tags:
  - motivatexr-runner

publish:
stage: publish
script:
  - # Trigger the Kubernetes Production Environment to update pods
only:
  - main
tags:
  - motivatexr-runner
```

The pipeline is designed to automate the workflow after merging changes into the dev branch:

- **Branches:** The only: - dev directive ensures that the pipeline runs only when changes are pushed to the dev branch, aligning with our branching strategy. Meanwhile the - main directive ensures that the pipeline runs only when changes are pushed to the main branch
- **Tags:** Each job specifies tags: - motivatexr-runner, directing the jobs to run on the self-hosted GitLab Runner.
- **Scripts:** The script section in each job contains the commands executed during that stage. These scripts are written in pseudocode for clarity but include actions such as building Docker images, running tests, logging into the Docker registry, pushing images, and triggering Kubernetes updates.

5.4 ENVIRONMENT VARIABLES AND SECURE CREDENTIALS

Sensitive data such as passwords and tokens are managed securely using GitLab's CI/CD variables. These variables are stored in the project's settings and are injected into the runner's environment at runtime. This approach confirms that sensitive information is not hard coded into the scripts or exposed in the repository.

5.5 NOTIFICATIONS AND MONITORING

Notifications can be set up to be sent to the development team to keep everyone informed about the pipeline status. These notifications, delivered via email or messaging platforms like Slack or Discord, provide real-time updates on the progress and outcomes of each stage. These notifications can be triggered after the successful completion of stages such as Deploy or Publish or by not passed test on Test stage or errors on the Deploy stage. Additionally, Gitlab provides tools to monitor the health and performance of the applications in both the staging and production environments.

6 AUTOMATED TEST

To check the reliability and robustness of our application architecture, which includes a headless CMS, an Identity Provider (IdP) for identity and access management, a database for data persistence and a Dashboard for end-users, a comprehensive suite of automated tests will be implemented. These tests will cover various aspects of the system to detect issues during the development cycle and maintain high-quality code throughout the project's lifecycle.

6.1 UNIT TESTS

Unit Tests will be written for individual components within the headless CMS, such as controllers, services, and models. These tests will verify that each unit of code functions correctly in isolation. For example, automated tests will verify that the CMS correctly handles all CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) operations for XR content, ensuring data integrity and consistency over individual API endpoints. In addition, unit tests will be created for any custom integrations with the IdP, verifying that authentication tokens are correctly processed, and that user roles and permissions are accurately interpreted within the CMS. For the dashboard, unit test for components and methods, must be created as well.

6.2 INTEGRATION TESTS

Integration Tests will focus on the interaction between the IdP, the CMS and the database. These tests will simulate real-world scenarios where multiple components work together, such as user

authentication flows, authorization checks, and data retrieval operations. The end-to-end authentication process should be tested, to ensure that users can log in via IdP and access protected resources in the CMS based on their assigned roles. Integration tests will also verify that data is correctly stored in and retrieved from the database when performing CRUD operations through the CMS API. The interaction between the frontend and CMS should be tested, verifying that API calls return the expected data and that the dashboard handles responses correctly.

6.3 DASHBOARD SPECIFIC TESTS

UI tests will verify that the visual elements of the dashboard render correctly across different devices and screen sizes. Automated security testing will detect vulnerabilities in the dashboard, test like cross-site scripting (XSS) or cross-site request forgery (CSRF).

7 TOOLS INTEGRATIONS

To gather the functional requirements for the CMS platform, a dedicated workshop was conducted during a technical meeting. The workshop was attended by representatives from seven MOTIVATE XR tools that plan to utilize the CMS for storing or retrieving XR content and for authentication purposes. The primary goal was to establish how the tools were going to integrate or interact with the platform.

The workshop lasted one hour and was structured into the following key segments.

7.1 PRESENTATION OF PLATFORM CAPABILITIES

The session began with a comprehensive presentation highlighting the various ways the CMS platform could support the tools. This included an overview of the platform's functionalities such as content management, authentication services, data processing capabilities, and integration options. The presentation aimed to provide participants with a clear understanding of how the platform could meet their specific needs.

7.2 INTERACTIVE MIRO BOARD SESSION

Following the presentation, an interactive Miro board was introduced to facilitate collaborative input. Each tool developer was provided with a template on the Miro board to specify their needs and requirements. The template included the following sections:

- **Tool Name and Description:** *Provide the name of your tool and a brief description of its functionality.*
- **Integration Method:** *Do you prefer integration via API, software development kit (SDK), webhooks, or other methods?*
- **Output/Input Expected:** *Is the data flow one-way or two-way between your tool and the CMS?*
- **Supported Data Formats:** *Which data formats does your tool support (e.g., JSON, XML, CSV, XR-specific formats)?*
- **Authentication and Security:** *Do you need to secure your API or authorization for your tool?*
- **Features Needed from CMS:** *List specific CMS functionalities you need access to (e.g., data cleaning, data augmentation).*
- **User Roles and Permissions:** *What levels of access will your tool require within the CMS?*
- **Monitoring and Analytics:** *Do you need access to analytics or logs related to the integration?*
- **Notification Preferences:** *Would you like to receive notifications for certain events (e.g., data updates, errors)?*
- **Other:** *Any other need or requirement your tool might have.*

This interactive session allowed each participant to articulate their specific requirements and preferences in a structured manner.

7.3 DISCUSSION AND FEEDBACK

After filling out their respective sections on the Miro board, the participants engaged in an open group discussion. This segment provided an opportunity to:

- **Discuss Integration Strategies:** The discussion facilitated an exchange of ideas on how best to integrate the tools with the CMS, considering factors like preferred data formats and authentication methods.
- **Clarify Requirements:** Participants elaborated on their inputs, providing additional context where necessary.
- **Identify Common Needs:** The group identified overlapping requirements and potential areas for shared solutions.

- **Address Potential Challenges:** Participants brought up any concerns or potential obstacles they foresaw in the integration process, allowing for proactive problem-solving.

FIGURE 1 MIRO BOARD FROM WORKSHOP

7.4 GENERAL OUTCOMES

The workshop successfully achieved its objectives:

- **Use of the platform:** Identified four different ways to interactor integrate the CMS on the different tools.
- **Integration approach:** Retrieved the first approach on how each tool will integrate the CMS.
- **Requirements Gathering:** Collected detailed functional requirements from each tool, providing valuable insights into the specific needs of the users.
- **Enhanced Collaboration:** Fostered a collaborative environment where participants could share ideas and build upon each other's inputs, strengthening the community around the platform.

- **Actionable Insights:** The feedback and discussions generated actionable insights that will inform the next steps in the platform's development, ensuring it aligns closely with user needs.

7.5 TOOLS INPUTS

The following outlines the inputs provided by each tool, from the filled templates.

7.5.1 KAYROX

Tool Name and Description	KAYROX
Integration Method:	API
Output/Input expected:	two-way, read and write content: media assets, experiences (json+assets)
Supported Data Formats	JSON, XML, CSV- 3d models: GLB, FBX - Images: jpg png svg- Video: mp4 webm - PDFs, Audio: mpe ogg
Authentication and Security	No
Features Needed from CMS	
User Roles and Permissions:	Offer contexts at the organization/company level and at the public level. At organization level, creator user, consumer user and administrator user.

Monitoring and Analytics:	Yes, especially if the plan of exploitation is to be pay-per-use.
Notification Preferences:	Yes, i.e. when a video to 3D process has finished, or a document has been processed to a KG
Other	Generative AI services

TABLE 2 KAYROX WORKSHOP OUTCOME

7.5.2 RTXR

Tool Name and Description	Remote Training System with Augmented Reality (RTXR)
Integration Method:	API or Via Dashboard
Output/Input expected:	Two-Way, read and write content
Supported Data Formats	JSON, 3D Models: FBX, Images: jpg, png, Videos: mp4 Audio: mp3
Authentication and Security	Server-side authorization ideally would be nice
Features Needed from CMS	Discuss further
User Roles and Permissions:	Need to be defined, Content creator, trainer-trainee, remote assistant.

Monitoring and Analytics:	Yes, would be nice.
Notification Preferences:	Yes, for data updates, (NE live function), training material uploaded, etc.
Other	Not at the moment

TABLE 3 RTXR WORKSHOP OUTCOME

7.5.3 MIRA

Tool Name and Description	MIRA - Digital twin platform
Integration Method:	API
Output/Input expected:	One way
Supported Data Formats	json. csv
Authentication and Security	Already implemented.
Features Needed from CMS	Discuss
User Roles and Permissions:	Existing roles in Mira relate to 1) owner 2) admin 3) user

Monitoring and Analytics:	Likely no
Notification Preferences:	Likely no
Other	-

TABLE 4 MIRA WORKSHOP OUTCOME

7.5.4 INSCAPE VTS EDITOR

Tool Name and Description	Inscape VTS Editor Authoring tool used to create design and publish an XR experience in internal format usable by Inscape VTS Player software. we have internal collaborative work capabilities.
Integration Method:	it's a software to be runned on a station and interactively used by the user (an editor), how do you integrate this ? via Dashboard
Output/Input expected:	Input : UE data from 3D models, IA extracted data / output : export XR experience (Inscape format), partial XR data export (generated for KAYROX)
Supported Data Formats	JSON, internal Inscape format
Authentication and Security	not sure, maybe
Features Needed from CMS	File storage and exchange, file versioning

User Roles and Permissions:	Author (creation, edition), trainer (edition)
Monitoring and Analytics:	not sure
Notification Preferences:	I don't see how we could manage them, so far
Other	...

TABLE 5 INSCAPE VTS EDITOR WORKSHOP OUTCOME

7.5.5 INSCAPE VTS PLAYER

Tool Name and Description	Inscape VTS Player: Application used to play an XR experience in internal format on display devices
Integration Method:	t's an application to be run on a station with a connected XR display, or run directly on the XR display, it needs to retrieve the XR experience files from storage.
Output/Input expected:	input : XR experience (Inscape format)
Supported Data Formats	internal Inscape format
Authentication and Security	not sure, maybe

Features Needed from CMS	Retrieval of XR experience files from data storage.
User Roles and Permissions:	trainee (playing)
Monitoring and Analytics:	not sure
Notification Preferences:	I don't see how we could manage them, so far
Other	...

TABLE 6 INSCAPE VTS PLAYER

7.5.6 CHATBOT

Tool Name and Description	Chatbot from Task 4.2
Integration Method:	API
Output/Input expected:	Documentations and an ontology. The output needs to be defined but there is a knowledge graph.
Supported Data Formats	For the documentation: pdf, docx, excel
Authentication and Security	Yes, because it could be costly to add a file of documentation and need to be correct (don't know if platform or their own)

Features Needed from CMS	Need to be defined
User Roles and Permissions:	Yes, Need to be defined
Monitoring and Analytics:	Need to be defined
Notification Preferences:	I think it could be interesting to have errors and when a new document is uploaded
Other	Need to be defined

TABLE 7 CHATBOT WORKSHOP OUTCOME

7.5.7 3D VIDEOGRAMMETRY SYSTEM

Tool Name and Description	<p>-XVS Scanner" Hardware is a 3D Scanning tool that can be used to scan areas by utilising the XVS Scanner.</p> <p>Other Hardware can be used like glasses or manual RGBD sensors, LiDAR..</p> <p>- Videogrammetry Software allows to enter videos and obtain 3D models. AI-based Segmentation 3D available. 3D processing in our Servers.</p>
Integration Method:	API
Output/Input expected:	<p>XVS App today: Input: mp4,2fc // Output:las, ply, obj,</p> <p>Others also are possible.</p>

Supported Data Formats	mp4, las, ply, obj, stl
Authentication and Security	Actually, it has a license code. Can be adapted.
Features Needed from CMS	Not sure
User Roles and Permissions:	Not Needed
Monitoring and Analytics:	Not Sure
Notification Preferences:	Not Sure
Other	Not at the moment

TABLE 8 3D VIDEOGRAMMETRY SYSTEM WORKSHOP OUTCOME

7.5.8 LEONARDOXR

Tool Name and Description	LeonardoXR - Headset for AR/XR
Integration Method:	APIs (for remote communication), but also SDK libraries (Unreal/Unity)

Output/Input expected:	Two-way data flow with the CMS
Supported Data Formats	JSON, 3D Models: FBX, Images: jpg, png, Videos: mp4, webm, Audio: mp3
Authentication and Security	I think the use of the headset should be secured, maybe via an access PIN code to input at the start of the app
Features Needed from CMS	TBD
User Roles and Permissions:	Access as user of the headset, viewer, author
Monitoring and Analytics:	It would be a nice feature to have analytics about the use of the headset
Notification Preferences:	At app level, notifications on errors or warnings are useful for debugging.
Other	Nothing

TABLE 9 LEONARDOXR WOKRSHOP OUTCOME

7.6 INTEGRATION OPTIONS

After analyzing the discussions and inputs gathered during the workshop, multiple methods of integration with the platform have been identified. By defining these use cases, the goal is to illustrate the platform's versatility and demonstrate how it effectively covers all the specific needs faced by MOTIVATE XR tools.

7.6.1 ACCESS VIA DASHBOARD

This integration method is designed for tools or applications that do not wish to integrate directly with the platform using the API. The dashboard offers an alternative method of interaction. Users can export their XR files from their tools and manually import them into the dashboard, and vice versa. This process provides flexibility, allowing users to continue utilizing their existing tools while still benefiting from the platform's centralized management and collaboration features.

The platform will offer a dashboard designed for managing assets, XR files and experiences. Accessible directly through web browsers, this dashboard provides a unified interface for all XR content management needs.

Aimed at individual users or teams who design and develop XR content—such as 3D artists, developers, and designers—the dashboard also serves team members, clients, or partners who require access to XR files for review, feedback, or contribution. This inclusive approach makes it easy to collaborate among all stakeholders involved in the XR creation process.

Users can log in to the dashboard via their web browser on any device using secure credentials, ensuring that their work remains protected. Once logged in, they can manage their XR files directly from the intuitive dashboard interface. This includes uploading new files, organizing assets efficiently or modify and updating metadata associated with their XR files easily.

By securing their work within the platform and making it accessible everywhere and anytime, users benefit from increased productivity and peace of mind. The dashboard's user-friendly design and powerful features streamline the XR content management process, empowering creators and collaborators to focus on bringing immersive experiences to life.

7.6.2 ACCESS VIA API

The platform will offer integration capabilities for third-party tools and applications, enabling MOTIVATE XR stakeholders to incorporate XR content management functionalities directly into their own solutions. By utilizing the platform's APIs, these external tools will be able to perform many of the same actions available on the platform's dashboard, such as uploading XR files, editing metadata, and more, all within their native environments.

This integration is designed for tool creators and developers who wish to integrate their applications with MOTIVATE XR. By connecting to the platform, they can focus on their tools while providing users with seamless access to XR content management features.

Developers will have two methods to integrate their tools with the platform, via Identity Provider (IdP) or via API Key Authentication.

7.6.2.1 IDENTITY PROVIDER

Developers can integrate their tools using OAuth through the IdP. This method involves redirecting users to a secure login and authorization process, where they grant the tool permission to access their data on the platform.

- **Use Cases:** Best suited for tools that need to perform actions on behalf of a user, such as personal content management, editing, or when accessing user-specific data.
- **Access Control:** OAuth provides user-authenticated endpoints, allowing the tool to perform any actions that the authenticated user is permitted to do on the platform.
- **Security Considerations:** OAuth ensures that users' credentials are not shared with the tool. Instead, the tool receives a token with specific permissions granted by the user, enhancing security and compliance with privacy standards.

7.6.2.2 API KEY AUTHENTICATION

Developers can authenticate their tools using API Key Authentication. In this method, the platform issues a unique API key to the developer, which the tool uses to authenticate its requests to the platform's API. This key acts as a credential that identifies the tool and grants it access to specific API endpoints appropriate for its designated role.

- **Use Cases:** Ideal for server-to-server interactions, automated processes, or when the tool operates independently of a user's direct input.
- **Access Control:** The API key provides access to endpoints suitable for the tool's functions, ensuring that it can perform necessary actions without overstepping permissions.
- **Security Considerations:** Developers must securely store and manage the API key to prevent unauthorized access. The key should be kept confidential and rotated periodically according to best practices.

7.7 INTEGRATION METHOD BY TOOL

In this initial version of the document, the most suitable integration method for each tool within the MOTIVATE XR ecosystem is presented. Some tools will integrate with the platform via API Key Authentication, enabling secure server-to-server communication and automated processes with controlled permissions. Others will utilize OAuth Authentication via an Identity Provider, allowing users to securely grant specific permissions for tools that perform actions on their behalf. Additionally, certain tools may prefer not to integrate directly with the platform's API and will instead use the dashboard method, manually exporting content from their tool and importing it into the dashboard, and vice versa. Please note that as this is the first version of the document, the integration methods and recommendations may evolve over time to better accommodate the diverse needs of the tools and users.

7.7.1 KAYROX

Tool	KAYROX
Description	Authoring Tool for Creating XR Experiences
Integration Method	OAuth Authentication via Identity Provider
Responsible	TECNALIA
Overview	<p>KAYROX is an advanced authoring tool designed for creating immersive XR experiences. It empowers designers, developers, and artists to craft interactive virtual and augmented reality content with ease. By integrating with the platform using OAuth Authentication via an Identity Provider, KAYROX allows users to seamlessly access and manage XR content directly within the tool, enhancing workflow efficiency and user experience.</p>

TABLE 10 KAYROX INTEGRATION

7.7.2 RTRX

Tool	RTRX
Description	Remote Training System with Augmented Reality
Integration Method	API Key Authentication
Responsible	DCUBE
Overview	
<p>RTRX is a remote training system that leverages augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) technologies to deliver immersive training experiences. Utilizing AR devices and virtual reality headsets, RTRX creates interactive and engaging learning environments that enhance user engagement and knowledge retention. By integrating with the platform via API Key Authentication, RTRX intends to securely interact with the platform's API to access and manage XR content, synchronize training modules, and handle user data efficiently.</p>	

TABLE 11 RTRX INTEGRATION

7.7.3 MIRA

Tool	MIRA
Description	Digital Twin Platform
Integration Method	OAuth Authentication via an Identity Provider
Responsible	Maggioli
Overview	
<p>MIRA is an authoring tool designed for creating and managing Digital Twins—virtual replicas of physical assets, processes, or systems. By integrating with the platform using OAuth Authentication via an Identity Provider, MIRA allows users to seamlessly access and manage their Digital Twin content directly within the tool, enhancing workflow efficiency and user experience.</p>	

TABLE 12 MIRA INTEGRATION

7.7.4 INSCAPE VTS EDITOR

Tool	Inscape Editor
Description	Authoring Platform for Interactive Storytelling
Integration Method	Dashboard
Responsible	CS
Overview	
<p>Inscape Editor is an authoring platform originating from the INSCAPE European RTD project, designed for creating interactive storytelling experiences. Integration with the platform will leverage the dashboard, allowing users to manually export and import content for seamless interaction with the MOTIVATE XR platform.</p>	

TABLE 13 INSCAPE VTS EDITOR INTEGRATION

7.7.5 INSCAPE VTS PLAYER

Tool	Inscape Player
Description	Authoring Platform for Interactive Storytelling
Integration Method	Dashboard
Responsible	CS
Overview	
<p>Inscape Player, a counterpart to the Inscape Editor, enables users to experience interactive storytelling content. Integration with the platform will utilize the dashboard for manual export and import of content, ensuring compatibility and ease of use within the MOTIVATE XR ecosystem.</p>	

TABLE 14 INSCAPE VTS PLAYER INTEGRATION

7.7.6 CHATBOT

Tool	Chatbot
Description	The AI-powered Document Conversion Assistant
Integration Method	API Key Authentication
Responsible	CS, UPM
Overview	
<p>The AI-powered Document Conversion Assistant analyzes technical documentation, including text and illustrations, to extract structured content for use in authoring tools. It utilizes advanced techniques like Large Language Models (LLMs) and deep neural networks to convert textual descriptions into knowledge graphs and to recognize and identify parts in visual content. Domain-specific thesauri or ontologies enhance its ability to structure information effectively. By integrating with the platform via API Key Authentication, the assistant securely uploads extracted content, manages thesaurus, processes documents and automates communication with the platform, ensuring efficient operation within the MOTIVATE XR ecosystem.</p>	

TABLE 15 CHATBOT INTEGRATION

7.7.7 3D VIDEOGRAMMETRY SYSTEM

Tool	3D Videogrammetry System
Description	3D Scanning and Modelling Tool for XR Devices
Integration Method	API Key Authentication
Responsible	2Freedom
Overview	
<p>The 3D Videogrammetry System, developed under the MOTIVATE XR project, combines specialized camera hardware and advanced software to prioritize photogrammetry and VSLAM (Visual Simultaneous Localization and Mapping) for creating high-resolution 3D</p>	

models. It outputs point clouds and meshes in LAS, PLY, and OBJ formats, supporting workflows for visualization and simulation. While formats like FBX, STEP, and GLB are not direct outputs, they can be generated through third-party applications. GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) integration adds precision for specific applications by combining GNSS data with external instruments through custom methods.

Building on these capabilities, the system is advancing in computer vision with plans to include real-time object detection and segmentation, enabling segmented areas to be exported as 3D objects. Additional LiDAR integration is being explored to capture homogeneous spaces, with potential export options in LAS, LAZ, and E57 formats. Future developments aim to incorporate Neural Radiance Fields (NeRFs) and Gaussian Splats for volumetric reconstruction and complex environment modeling. Semi-automated BIM (Building Information Modeling) and CAD (Computer-Aided Design) workflows are also planned to expand functionality. The tool currently uses a licence-based access system, with plans to add API functionality in the future to enable easier integration with other software.

TABLE 16 3D VIDEOGRAMMETRY SYSTEM INTEGRATION

7.7.8 LEONARDO XR

Tool	Leonardo XR
Description	3D Scanning and Modelling Tool for XR Devices
Integration Method	Dashboard
Responsible	YBQ
Overview	<p>Leonardo XR is an XR helmet designed for advanced remote assistance, enabling fast and reliable diagnostics, as well as immersive training in real-world scenarios. Leonardo XR will integrate with the platform via API, however, due to the difficulties associated with login interfaces on XR devices, a new authentication method should be designed. To address this issue, a hybrid authentication approach combining long-lived OAuth tokens with a PIN or QR coded could be proposed. This method will allow users to authenticate securely and simplify the login process to interact with the platform's API to access and manage XR content.</p>

TABLE 17 LEONARDOXR INTEGRATION

8 CONCLUSIONS

With this document, the continuous integration plan for the staging environment has been clearly defined, providing a structured workflow for building, testing, and deploying the components of the MOTIVATE XR ecosystem. It also presents a preliminary definition of how various tools and applications will interact with the platform, setting the basis for further refinement and allowing teams to move forward with a shared understanding of the integration approach.

The next deliverable will focus on detailing the integration plan for the production environment. The methods by which tools will authenticate, exchange data, and operate within MOTIVATE XR in a live setting will be defined. It is anticipated that some adjustments may be necessary as the project evolves and tools feedback and experiences will be considered.